

Implementation Of The «Museum Shop» In Museums Of Uzbekistan: Experience

Ismailova Jannat Khamidovna

Director of the State Museum of history of Uzbekistan, doctor of historical sciences, professor

ORCID:0000-0002-5846-3716

Abstract: *This article discusses the implementation of museum store projects in the development of museum activities and the improvement of museum management based on the experience of local museums in foreign countries. The possibilities of the practice of fundraising into the practice of museums in Uzbekistan are also shown.*

Keywords — Museum store, fundraising, museum tourism, cultural tourism, museum marketing, art market, museum hydraulic structures, traveling exhibitions.

INTRODUCTION.

The problem of collecting museum objects and passing them on to future generations has never been as important for society as it is now. The increasing level of globalization, radical transformations in the surrounding reality change the place in the material culture of man, his personality and history, requires clarification of ways and conditions of explaining and describing these changes. Museums have always served as a platform of ideological development of generations, a source of knowledge, upbringing and education in different historical periods.

The preservation and display of museum objects has become one of the most important tasks in modern context of globalization, which means that every nation has a deeper understanding of its history and culture. In this regard, strengthening the material and technical base of museums is one of the actual issues. To this end, it is important to develop a targeted plan for the construction, reconstruction, repair and equipping of state museums with modern technology and improving the exposition and collection capacity in 2023-2026.

The Agency for Cultural Heritage, the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Construction jointly should develop a standard design for art galleries. It is important to organize an exhibition hall, training and creative rooms for young people, a modern library-café, and art workshops for creators.

In a post-industrial society, the transformation of cultural values into international goods is considered as a component of cultural and economic development and an economic resource. Tourism, international festivals and museum projects are the main means of establishing cultural exports. One of the most striking processes of exporting the culture of a particular people of the world is tourism. It is important to note that the tourism business or the tourism industry does not prepare a new product for the material needs of a person. He "decorates", advertises and sells the culture of the nation.

The development and improvement of additional services in museums has great importance in the development of museum tourism and creative entrepreneurship, attracting investment in museum activities, introducing the practice of fundraising in nonprofit art institutions, managing cultural projects, improving intellectual property relations, and expanding the scope of art productions.

The international exhibitions and festivals "Sharq taronalari" ("Sounds of the East"), "Asrlar sadosi" ("Sounds of Centuries"), "Biennale" regularly organized in the republic are significant not only for their ideological and creative features, but also for the great influence they have on the development of cultural exports. The "cultural (creative) industry" widely used in the West. This, in turn, serves to restore national values and thereby enrich cultural resources. In the 21st century, which is considered the age of information, the active activity and initiative of museums in international festivals and large-scale projects is important. At the same time, such issues as the concept of museum development, the formation of museum marketing and management will again intersect. Every year major festivals are organized in Russia, such as "Children's Day in Museums of St. Petersburg", "Night in Museums" or "Contemporary Art in Traditional Museums". This will certainly affect the cooperation of the country's museums, the exchange of experience and achievements.

Globalization of the economy, uniqueness of the post-industrial society and dominance of the service sector over the production sphere also influenced cultural tourism and developed the art market. In this context a new type of tourism appeared, i.e. Museum tourism [2]. Internal mobilization of museum tourism and adaptation to market conditions, formation of business policy and determination of strategy, establishment of external relations served as an important tool in the development of marketing policy of famous museums. Museums implement new forms of interaction with the audience, paying more and more attention to the common interests of the museum audience in the development of their activities.

Literature review. The studies of P. Michael, M. Bryden and J. Hall for the first time were devoted to the economy of

tourism of the second half of the twentieth century in the European countries, recommendations on free tourists, problems connected with development of projects in the organization of marketing system in museum tourism [3]. They mainly reflect the development and problems of souvenir trade in museum tourism on the basis of many years of observations and practical experience of the authors in the sphere of tourism.

The description of extensive works in the field of museum tourism, its planning, marketing and management of this sphere, as well as regional features, forms of work with visitors, specific aspects of innovative tourism development are considered on the experience of European museums. The significance of these studies served as an important source for studying the prospects of applying foreign experience related to the development of museums in cultural and educational tourism in Uzbekistan. The authors presented some statistical and factual data on the adaptation of museum objects to tourism, based on the conservation of historical objects in the practice of museification.

Within the framework of the study, the creation of curatorial projects in the development of cultural tourism, the study of museum communication, the organization of museum and display festivals in the system of ethnographic and art museums, management and practical developments in the financial development of museum stores as well as dissertations conducted in such research centers as the USA, England and France [5]. In the first half of the 21st century, based on the experience of museums of various specializations, modern areas of activity and innovative solutions for the development of museum tourism were investigated.

Research Methodology. The development of museum souvenir products and the expansion of its assortment are considered to be one of the most significant problems today. It is very difficult to classify the existing range of products for tourists, because it is important to constantly update new objects and products that attract the attention of tourists. Starting this year, state museums have created opportunities to purchase copies of exhibits and collections in their "museum stores". The world of museum sales has undergone major changes in recent years. "There are 104 museums and their branches in the Cultural Heritage Agency system, including 37 main museums and 67 branches. There are 7 museum-reserves and 12 house-museums. During 2020-2021 the development of the museum industry focused on the active application of information technologies in the digitalization industry. In particular, in 2020, the electronic catalog system of the National Museum Fund (www.davkatalog.uz) was created, and 46 state museums were added into the catalog. In 2021, 229,677 museum objects and collections were identified electronically. Using the latest IT-technology for the roundme.com platform, museums located in Tashkent were digitized exhibits in 3D format in a new quality standard - the size of 12K (the "Virtual Museum" project). Filming was conducted in more than 18 museums and posted on the world's largest platform roundme.com, as well as vrmuseum.uz (TasIX). Since 2022, the practice of approving calendar plans

of exhibitions, traveling exhibitions, cultural and educational events, forums, conferences and seminars organized in the museums of the republic was introduced. There is also a system of evaluation of museums' activities".

Also the Agency of Cultural Heritage created a working group to organize a "Museum shop" system in museums and cultural heritage sites in tourist destinations. This working group is developing proposals to study experience of such countries as Turkey, China, France, USA on organization of "Museum shop" and introduction of their advanced experience to Uzbekistan. It is planned to develop unique brands and trade marks of museums, replicas of unique museum items in "Museum stores" in each museum. [6].

Nowadays, the range of foreign museum stores has expanded considerably, and they present not only art albums, notebooks, toys and fridge magnets, but also clothing, designer furnitures, selective perfumes, electronic gadgets, jewelry, sculpture copies, rare editions of graphics by subscription are also available. Secondly, museum stores have begun to operate as separate retail outlets. The New York Museum of Modern Art (MoMa) has six sales offices: three in the United States, two in Japan and one in Hong Kong. Museum souvenirs are sold online not only on museum websites, but also in other tourist markets. All of this has led to a rethinking of the role of the museum exhibit and now museum stores form the basis of the museum's marketing system. Through logo souvenirs, museums promote their brand, ideology and values. According to the American Association of Museum Stores, sales of memorabilia bring museums from 5 to 25% of their annual income [7].

Despite the relevance of the issue of "souvenir" products in the sphere of museum tourism, fundamental scientific and practical studies on the study and generalization of the multifaceted practice of creating souvenir products with different functionalities have not been conducted. The same situation is observed in the marketing of souvenir products (modeling, consumer evaluation, sales culture, etc.).

Today, there is a rich and diverse range of souvenir products for every tourist, based on his financial capabilities, the range of interests, etc. It can be calendars, magnets, trinkets, stationery, badges, phone cases, banners, stickers, etc., as well as folk art products, clothing, jewelry and costume jewelry, interior items, art albums, books, etc.

Among the traditional marketing tools used in museums, the creation of museum souvenirs should be emphasized, which is one of the additional opportunities to advertise this institution and subsequently increase its attractiveness. The main functions of souvenirs (besides the functional purpose of the object):

presentation and advertising of the brand, the formation of the image of the organization, the formation of the image of the buyer of the souvenir;

aesthetic and artistic value;

gift and demonstration of loyalty to partner organizations.

The most common and sorted souvenirs in museums are:

items depicting museum symbols (views of buildings, collectibles, or portraits of historical figures related to museum activities);

souvenirs with the symbols of the museum's territorial affiliation;

souvenirs of a museum profile;

printed and multimedia museum materials (e.g., catalogs, books, manuals, CDs) are also souvenirs. Many museums build and strengthen their reputation in the research environment, acting as publishers.

Thus, by distributing their souvenirs, museums expand their audience, attract visitors, professional communities and patrons.

Most of the museum souvenirs are devoted to the main exhibition, in rare cases souvenirs dedicated to specific events are created. A souvenir is a way to communicate with the tourist, which is functionally defined by the following aspects:

- Encouraging tourists to visit the museum again;
- focusing on folk art, traditional festivals and rituals, handicrafts;
- creating demand for traditional production, economic activities and handicrafts.

Analysis and results. In order to ensure the fulfillment of tasks specified in the "Address plan" of additional services organized in state museums for 2022-2023, approved by the Annex to the Presidential Decree of May 27, 2022 "On measures to develop services in museums" since June 2022, "Museum shop" and trade and craft workshops were launched in a number of museums. Including:

Bukhara State Museum-Reserve "ARK", Regional Museum of History and Local Lore, Museum of Applied Decorative and Applied Arts "Sitorai Mohi Khossa", Museum "History of Ancient Varakhsha and Pottery", Museum and Workshop "History of Bukhara Blacksmithcraft", "Gilambofliki" the museum was allocated 10 souvenir and gift shops, craft workshops and trade outlets with a total area of 110 sq. m [9].

In the Shakhrisabz state museum-reserve 110 square meters of area were allocated, 3 souvenir and souvenir shops, craft workshops and retail outlets were opened [10].

In the Kokand state museum-reserve 1 - porch 1,60x3,10, 2 - porch on the passage 2,20x3,10, 3, 3,90x4,55 square meters from the gatehouse are arranged craftsman workshop and retail outlets. The stores and retail outlets sold various souvenirs made from unique museum items, albums and catalogs published by the museum, as well as handicrafts and other souvenirs [11].

In the foyer of the State Art Museum of Uzbekistan on an area of 20 square meters there is a gift and souvenir store, a craftsman's workshop and sales offices. Here souvenirs of

different types are made from unique and special exhibits of the museum. The store also has catalogs published by the museum [12]. To date, the following system of merchandising related to museum activities has been established in the souvenir stores of this museum:

- To the 100th anniversary of the State Art Museum of Uzbekistan porcelain dishes with images of Russian and Central Asian avant-garde works in the museum;
- postcards of avant-garde works in the museum for the 100th anniversary of the State Art Museum of Uzbekistan;
- Souvenirs with images of unique paintings of the State Art Museum of Uzbekistan [13].

A souvenir store was also opened at the State Museum of the History of Uzbekistan. This store is located in the lobby of the museum, and its area is 7 square meters. Reconstruction of the building of the State Museum of History of Uzbekistan is carried out jointly with the Tashkent city council and specialists of the Turkish company "Outdoor Factory". In a new project of the museum building it is planned to create a souvenir shop and a "Book Cafe" that meets modern requirements. Souvenirs of the museum are made on the basis of museum items from the Bronze Age to the Middle Ages. Currently, souvenirs are made on the basis of more than 20 exhibits, and it is planned to produce many copies of them [14].

Conclusion/Recommendations. A catalog purchased in a museum store, a gift, a video, or even a special shopper can serve as advertising. Leaving the museum, these emblematic names do an important job of reminding the person the visit to the museum, and they remind everyone passing by that the museum exists. A museum can always expand its potential audience; in today's world, there is no limit to the dissemination of knowledge. Television, video, electronic catalogs and other communication technologies enable a museum to reach its clients, bypassing geographical barriers. Decentralization, refusal of directive management, fuller realization of the rule "work on itself", i.e. separation of representatives of state power from recipients of funds and distribution of these funds through self-government of public funds are observed in the practice of modern world museums, thus, undoubtedly, financing of museums and generally remains a priority principle of state policy in the sphere of culture.

6. Carbohydrates increase in the cell cytoplasm and decrease the amount of water.

When the plant is dehydrated and thirsty in field conditions, high temperature has a fatal effect on it. When the leaves of a plant or its whole body wither a lot, a number of other physiological processes are disturbed, in addition to profound changes in the processes of photosynthesis and respiration. The resistance of the plant to the high temperature of atmospheric air depends on its ontogeny - the periods of growth and development. The greatest destructive effect of high temperature corresponds to the initial periods of growth and development. Actively developing young tissues are less resistant to high temperatures than old, old, "resting" ones.

Different parts of the plant have different resistance to high temperature: the underground part is less resistant, the stem, branch, buds are somewhat more resistant.

He quickly begins to adapt to heat stress that occurs in plants. The plant starts preparing for the effect of high temperature several hours earlier. When the days are hot, the resistance of plants to its high temperature is stronger after choshgoh, and weaker before choshgoh. Usually, this resistance is not stable, it does not get stronger, it disappears when the air temperature drops.

During the formation of generative organs in plants, resistance to high temperature decreases in annual and biennial plants.

The harmful effect of high temperature is especially strong on plants growing in dry conditions. For example, the formation of spikes begins during the period of wheat. A high temperature in the soil and atmospheric air causes damage to the growth cone, as a result of which the number of spikes, the amount of flowers in it decreases, and the yield in the provard is significantly reduced. The occurrence of drought in the soil due to the decrease of moisture in it, the high temperature of the air during the formation of spikes in grain plants causes damage to the flower buds in it, and the end of spike formation, it causes it to dry up. As a result, the number of ears without grain increases. For most of the plants, the high temperature of the atmosphere is dangerous, especially during their flowering period, it causes the flower to drop, the node does not develop, and it causes sterility. To determine the resistance of plants to high temperature, the studied plant leaf is placed in a chamber with high humidity and temperature for a certain period of time. The resistance is determined according to the signs of wounds formed on the leaves, branches and other places of the plant. According to F. F. Moskov method, the studied plant is taken from the leaf and placed in water with a temperature of 40, 45, 50 to 80 °C for 30 minutes. After 30 minutes, remove the leaf and put it in cold water for 10 minutes. After that, 0.2 normal is transferred to HC1 solution. Infected and dried areas of the leaf turn brown. The number of them is determined by determining the surface and how much they can withstand. In addition, resistance to high temperatures can be determined by the conductivity of protoplasm. A decrease in conductivity determines the inability to with stand high temperatures.

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